

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FORMULATION AND INVITRO EVALUATION OF
BROMOCRIPTINE MESYLATE NON EFFERVESCENT
FLOATING TABLETS****Pasupuleti Himabindu¹, K. Kishore², Dr. Gampa Vijay Kumar³**^{1,2,3}KGR Institute of Technology And Management, Rampally, Kesara, Rangareddy,
Telangana, India.**Abstract:**

The objective of this work was to evaluate the potential for Non-effervescent Floating drug delivery system (FDDS) of Bromocriptine Mesylate tablets prepared by using various polymers for reduction in the dosing frequency and possible increased bioavailability. Initially analytical method development was done for the drug molecule. Absorption maxima was determined based on that calibration curve, developed by using different concentrations. Gas generating agent sodium bicarbonate concentration was optimized. Then the formulation was developed by using different concentrations of polymers Gellan gum, Methocel K4M & Methocel K15M. Direct compression was used for preparation of Non effervescent floating tablets. Among all the formulations the formulation (F6) prepared with Methocel K4M retarded the drug release of 97.45% up to 12 hours in the concentration of 7.5 mg. The formulations prepared with Gellan gum & Methocel K15M were unable to retard the drug release up to 12 hours. From the release kinetics data it was evident that the formulation followed Peppas mechanism of drug release.

Keywords: Bromocriptine mesylate, Gellan gum, Methocel K4 M, Methocel K15 M and Floating tablets.

Corresponding author:**Kamere Kishore**, M. Pharm, (Ph.D)

Assistant Professor,

Department of Pharmacy,

KGR Institute of Management And Technology.

Email ID: kishorekgritm@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Kamere Kishore et al., *Formulation and Invitro Evaluation of Bromocriptine Mesylate Non Effervescent Floating Tablets.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Bromocriptine is a semisynthetic ergot alkaloid that interacts with D2 dopamine receptors to inhibit spontaneous and TRH-induced release of prolactin. It is used in neuroleptic malignant syndrome, acromegaly, infertility, hyperprolactinemia, prolactinoma, parkinson's disease, and type 2 diabetes mellitus (it was approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in May 2009, for the treatment of type 2 diabetes). It is rapidly absorbed after oral administration and has low systemic bioavailability about 28%. Bromocriptine has a relatively short elimination half-life (2-8 hours). The aim of this study is to prepare sustained release Bromocriptine Mesylate tablets utilizing the gastroretentive floating drug delivery system by non effervescent technique.

Materials

Bromocriptine Mesylate, Gellan gum, Methocel K4M, Methocel K15M, Sodium bicarbonate, Sodium Bicarbonate, Magnesium Stearate, Micro Crystalline Cellulose, Talc all the chemicals used were laboratory grade.

Methodology**Formulation Development of Tablets:****Table 1: Optimization sodium bicarbonate concentration**

S.No	Excipient Name	EF1	EF2	EF3
1	Bromocriptine mesylate	2.5	2.5	2.5
2	Methocel K15 M	5	5	5
3	NaHCO ₃	5	10	15
4	Magnesium Stearate	3	3	3
5	Talc	3	3	3
6	MCC pH 102	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S
	Total weight	60	60	60

All the quantities were in mg.

Based on the floating lag time and floating duration the concentration of sodium bicarbonate was optimised.

All the formulations were prepared by direct compression. The composition of different formulations is given in Table 2. The tablets were prepared as per the procedure given below and aim is to prolong the release of Bromocriptine Mesylate. Total weight of the tablet was considered as 60mg.

Procedure:

- 1) Bromocriptine Mesylate and all other ingredients were individually passed through sieve no \square 60.
- 2) All the ingredients were mixed thoroughly by triturating up to 15 min.
- 3) The powder mixture was lubricated with talc.
- 4) The tablets were prepared by using direct compression method.

Optimization of Sodium bicarbonate concentration:

Sodium bicarbonate was employed as effervescent gas generating agent. It helps the formulation to float. Various concentrations of sodium bicarbonate were employed; floating lag time and floating duration were observed. Based on that, the concentration of sodium bicarbonate was finalized and preceded for further formulations.

Table 2: Formulation composition for floating tablets

Formulation No.	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Bromocriptine mesylate	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Gellangum	2.5	5	7.5	----	----	----	----	----	----
MethocelK 4 M	----	----	----	2.5	5	7.5	----	----	----
MethocelK 15 M	----	----	----	----	----	----	2.5	5	7.5
NaHCO ₃	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Magnesium Stearate	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Talc	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Microcrystalline cellulose	QS								

All the quantities were in mg, Total weight is 60 mg.

Evaluation of prepared tablets

The designed formulation tablets were studied for their physicochemical properties like weight variation, hardness, thickness, friability, *In-vitro* release and drug content.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Analytical Method

Graphs of Bromocriptine mesylate was taken in Simulated Gastric fluid (pH 1.2) at 266 nm.

Table 3: Observations for graph of Bromocriptine mesylate in 0.1N HCl (266 nm)

Conc [$\mu\text{g/l}$]	Abs
0	0
1	0.131
2	0.232
3	0.377
4	0.519
5	0.629
6	0.764

Figure 1: Standard graph of Bromocriptine mesylate in 0.1N HCl

Preformulation Parameters of Powder Blend

Table 4: Pre-formulation parameters of blend

Formulation Code	Angle of Repose	Bulk density (g/mL)	Tapped density (g/mL)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
F1	24.02	0.51	0.55	16.34	1.11
F2	25.82	0.53	0.61	16.18	0.99
F3	23.24	0.51	0.67	17.32	0.68
F4	24.23	0.56	0.62	17.61	1.04
F5	25.21	0.52	0.65	16.88	1.22
F6	24.11	0.55	0.62	17.26	1.07
F7	26.06	0.57	0.67	16.33	0.85
F8	26.52	0.42	0.58	17.91	1.14
F9	25.49	0.52	0.61	17.64	1.18

Tablet powder blend was subjected to various pre-formulation parameters. The angle of repose values indicates that the powder blend has good flow properties. The bulk density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.42 to 0.57 (gm/mL) showing that the powder has good flow properties. The tapped density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.55 to 0.67 showing the powder has good flow properties. The compressibility index of all the formulations was found to be ranging between 16 to 18, which show that, the powder has good flow properties. All the formulations has shown the Hausner's ratio ranging between 0 to 1.2 indicating the powder has good flow properties.

Optimization of Sodium Bicarbonate Concentration:

Three formulations were prepared with varying concentrations of sodium bicarbonate. The formulation containing sodium bicarbonate in 10mg concentration showed less floating lag time of 4 min and the tablet was in floating condition for more than 12 hours.

Quality Control Parameters For Tablets:

Tablet quality control tests such as weight variation, hardness, friability, thickness and drug release studies in different media were performed on the tablets.

Table 5. *In vitro* quality control parameters for tablets

Formulation code	Weight variation (mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%loss)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)	Floating lag time (min)	Floating time (hrs)
F1	62.5	3.5	0.53	4.8	98.34	4.1	> 12 hrs
F2	65.4	3.2	0.52	3.9	99.67	4.4	> 12 hrs
F3	58.6	3.4	0.53	3.9	98.42	4.2	> 12 hrs
F4	60.6	3.5	0.54	3.9	99.74	4.0	> 12 hrs
F5	69.4	3.4	0.55	3.7	98.16	4.2	> 12 hrs
F6	60.7	3.2	0.48	3.5	99.54	4.4	> 12 hrs
F7	62.3	3.1	0.50	3.4	98.23	4.4	> 12 hrs
F8	61.2	3.3	0.48	3.7	98.58	4.6	> 12 hrs
F9	58.3	3.5	0.52	3.6	98.72	4.5	> 12 hrs

All the parameters such as weight variation, friability, hardness, thickness and drug content were found to be within limits.

In Vitro Drug Release Studies

Table 6: Dissolution Data of Bromocriptine mesylate Tablets F1 to F9

Time (Hrs)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	2.11	6.12	18.51	9.77	12.14	9.21	14.21	8.11	5.12
1	8.15	15.45	22.15	17.51	23.16	21.8	21.55	17.5	10.22
2	15.21	20.47	28.55	23.4	28.77	29.21	22.47	22.85	18.21
3	29.54	25.44	32.14	28.14	32.47	35.11	35.11	28.14	28.77
4	33.47	30.14	38.74	32.11	38.64	39.45	40.94	33.14	34.57
5	37.64	35.79	42.44	36.97	42.97	48.21	45.71	36.47	36.11
6	42.55	40.78	48.71	41.97	46.12	53.77	55.87	42.64	39.14
7	48.31	45.88	58.64	48.79	50.77	59.34	59.44	49.66	42.15
8	53.11	60.22	66.54	52.77	52.74	65.77	61.47	52.77	46.78
9	56.47	63.48	71.24	55.94	58.44	72.64	69.14	56.52	49.14
10	62.44	69.47	82.14	61.87	75.32	89.54	73.41	62.99	59.14
11	68.21	73.44	86.14	69.77	85.11	93.11	79.41	68.14	69.14
12	88.54	92.14	90.14	85.22	95.21	97.45	83.41	88.34	76.12

Figure2: Dissolution profile of Bromocriptine mesylate floating tablets (F1 to F9 formulations).

From the dissolution data it was evident that the formulations (Formulation F6) prepared with Methocel K4M retarded the drug release in the concentration of 7.5 mg showed required release pattern i.e., retarded the drug release up to 12 hours and showed maximum of 97.45 % in 12 hours with good floating lag time and floating buoyancy time.

The formulations prepared with Guar gum showed more retardation even after 12 hours they were not

shown total drug release. Hence they were not considered.

Application Of Release Rate Kinetics To Dissolution Data:

Various models were tested for explaining the kinetics of drug release. To analyze the mechanism of the drug release rate kinetics of the dosage form, the obtained data were fitted into zero-order, first order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas release model.

Table 7: Release kinetics data for optimised formulation (F6)

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG (%) RELEASE	LOG (T))	LOG (%) REMAIN
0	0	0	0	0	2.000
9.21	0.5	0.000	0.964	0.000	1.958
21.8	1	1.000	1.338	0.000	1.893
29.21	2	1.414	1.466	0.301	1.850
35.11	3	1.732	1.545	0.477	1.812
39.45	4	2.000	1.596	0.602	1.782
48.21	5	2.236	1.683	0.699	1.714
53.77	6	2.449	1.731	0.778	1.665
59.34	7	2.646	1.773	0.845	1.609
65.77	8	2.828	1.818	0.903	1.534
72.64	9	3.000	1.861	0.954	1.437
89.54	10	3.162	1.952	1.000	1.020
93.11	11	3.317	1.969	1.041	0.838
97.45	12	3.464	1.989	1.079	0.407

Figure 3 : Zero order release kinetics graph

Figure 4 : Higuchi release kinetics graph

Figure5: Kars mayerpeppas graph

Figure6: First order release kinetics graph

From the above graphs it was evident that the Formulation F6 followed Peppas mechanism.

CONCLUSION:

In the present research work non effervescent floating tablets of Bromocriptine mesylate were formulated by using various hydrophilic polymers. Initially an absorption maximum was determined. Based on that calibration curve was developed by using different concentrations. Gas generating agent sodium bicarbonate concentration was optimized. Then the formulation was developed by using different concentrations of various polymers. The formulation blend was subjected to various preformulation studies, flow properties and all the formulations were found to be good indicating that the powder blend has good flow properties. Among all the formulations the formulations prepared with Methocel K4 M retarded the drug release up to 12 hours in the concentration of 7.5 mg (F6). The formulations prepared by using Gellan gum & Methocel K15M were unable to retard drug release up to 12 hours. Hence they were not considered. The optimized formulation dissolution data was subjected to release kinetics; from the release kinetics data it was evident that the formulation followed Peppas mechanism of drug release.

REFERENCES:

- 1) Afshan Meherose and G. Udaya Bhanu Formulation And *In Vitro* Evaluation Of Floating Effervescent Tablets Of Ranitidine Hydrochloride IJPSR (2015), Vol. 6, Issue 12
- 2) Mohammed Asif Hussain Mahender B Maimuna Anjum Formulation and Evaluation of effervescent floating matrix tablets of Ofloxacin

Int. J. Drug Dev. & Res., January - March 2014, 6 (1): 188-198

- 3) Rakesh Pahwa, Lovely Chhabra, Avneet Kaur Lamba, Sumit Jindal and Arvind Rathour Formulation and *In vitro* evaluation of effervescent floating tablets of an antiulcer agent Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research, 2012, 4(2):1066-1073
- 4) Md. Haider Ali¹, Mohiuddin Ahmed Bhuiyan², Md. Selim Reza³ and Samira Karim¹ Formulation and *In vitro* Evaluation of Oral Floating Tablets of Salbutamol Sulphate: Comparison with Effervescent Tablets Dhaka Univ. J. Pharm. Sci. 15(2): 203-208, 2016 (December)
- 5) C Haranath, J Raveendra Reddy, N Devanna. Formulation and *In Vitro* Evaluation of Effervescent Floating Tablets of an Antibacterial Drug. *Inventi Impact: Pharm Tech*, 2016(4):145-151, 2016.
- 6) Akhlak Ahmed, Narendra Kr. Goyal and Pramod K. Sharma Effervescent Floating Drug Delivery System: A Review *Global Journal of Pharmacology* 8 (4): 478-485, 2014
- 7) Ali Raza, Nadeem Irfan Bukhari, Sabiha Karim y, Muhammad Ahsan Hafiz, Uzma Hayat Floating tablets of minocycline hydrochloride: Formulation, *In vitro* evaluation and optimization *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 3 (2017) 131e139
- 8) K. Chaitanya, Sellappan Velmurugan

- Formulation And Evaluation Of Levodopa Effervescent Floating Tablets Int J Pharm Pharm Sci, Vol 7, Issue 5, 189-193
- 9) KomuravellySomeshwar Kalyani Chithaluru, Tadikonda Ramarao K. K. Kalyan Kumar Formulation and evaluation of effervescent floating tablets of tizanidine hydrochloride Acta Pharm. 61 (2011) 217–226
 - 10) Harsharan Pal Singh, Ashmeet Kaur , Ishpreet Kaur Formulation and evaluation of effervescent floating tablet of famotidine with natural polymer chitosan Asian Pac. J. Health Sci., 2014; 1(4): 517-523
 - 11) Ali Kadivar , Behnam Kamalidehghan , Hamid Akbari Javar , Ehsan TaghizadehDavoudi , Nurul Dhaniah Zaharuddin , BaharehSabeti , Lip Yong Chung , Mohamed Ibrahim Noordin Formulation and *In vitro*, *In vivo* Evaluation of Effervescent Floating Sustained-Release Imatinib Mesylate Tablet PLOS ONE | DOI:10.1371/journal.pone.0126874 June 2, 2015
 - 12) S. R. Dawange, S. S. Khadabadi, S. S. Saboo Formulation and Evaluation of Floating Tablets of Verapamil Hydrochloride by using Gastroretentive Technology Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res., 34(1), September – October 2015; Article No. 42, Pages: 263-269
 - 13) Chordiya Mayur Ashok, Gangurde Hemant Hiranman , K . Senthilkumaran Formulation And *In vitro* Evaluation Of Effervescent Floating Matrix Tablet Of Propafenone Hcl World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences Volume 2, Issue 6, 5348-5362
 - 14) Ajay Kumar, AshniVerma,Geetika Sharma, Rupinder Saini, Shivani Sharma, Sukhdev Singh, Upendra K Jain, Mandeep Sharma Formulation and Characterization of Effervescent Floating Matrix Tablets of Famotidine Hydrochloride Asian Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences; 3(25) 2013, 43-47.
 - 15) Sarat Chandra Prasad Malisetty, Ravi Teja Allena, Swetha Sandina, HV Gangadharappa Formulation and evaluation of modified-release effervescent floating tablets of ofloxacin International Journal of Health & Allied Sciences • Vol. 2 • Issue 2 • Apr-Jun 2013